

ISic0105

I.Sicily inscription 0105

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

'fra le macerie di quell'antico castello'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]re[---]
2. [---]I,I in pub[---]
3. [---]ut ex p[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284840

EDR 110878

EDCS 10900636

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 23
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